

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15735021

Examination Anxiety As Correlate Of Academic Performance In Public Secondary Schools In Anambra State

Amuzie, Ukamaka Angela & Prof. Obikeze Nnamdi

**Department of Guidance and Counselling
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria.**

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the relationship between examination anxiety as correlate of academic performance of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in Anambra State. The population of the study comprised 21,272 senior secondary school two (SSII) students in the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population comprised of 21,272 students (9550 male students and 11,722 female students) in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of the study was 376 (161 male and 215 female) secondary school students in the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A multistage sampling technique was employed to determine the sample of the study. The instruments for data collection were two standardized rating scales; Westside Test Anxiety Scale (WTAS) by Driscoll (2004) and Academic Performance Scale (APS) by Birchmeier et al. (2015). The instruments were face and constructed validated by three experts, one from Measurement and Evaluation while two from Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. Furthermore, the construct validity of the instruments were ascertained using the Principal Component Analysis approach with Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) as a measure of sampling adequacy. The coefficient value of 0.754 was obtained. The reliability of the instruments were established through a trial test. The data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha. This yielded co-efficient values of 0.88 for Westside Test Anxiety Scale (WTAS), and 0.90 for Academic Performance Scale. Pearson Product Moment Correlational correlation and multiple regression were used to analyze data for the study. The finding of the study revealed that there was a low negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among secondary school students in Anambra State. The study found a low positive relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among male students, and a low negative relationship among female students. Furthermore, there was a significant negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Anambra State Also, there was a significant positive relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among male secondary school students and the negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of female secondary school students in Anambra State was statistically significant. Based on these findings, the researchers recommended among others that administrators of public secondary schools should in collaboration with the school guidance counsellor(s) introduce structured anxiety management programmes for students.

Keywords: Examination Anxiety, Academic Performance, Gender, Secondary School, Students

INTRODUCTION

Academic performance refers to the extent to which students achieve their educational goals across various domains, including academic knowledge, character development, communication skills, cultural understanding, and extracurricular activities. It is a multidimensional construct that reflects the outcomes of students' engagement with formal education, often measured through examinations, assessments, and overall progress in meeting learning objectives. Akinnola and Oredein (2021) defined academic performance as the successful completion of educational goals, typically demonstrated through assessments and examination results. Similarly, Bossaert and Doumen (in Akinnola & Oredein, 2021) viewed academic performance as the degree to which students, teachers, or institutions meet short- or long-term educational objectives. In Anambra State, academic performance has become a significant area of concern, particularly within public secondary schools. Observations by the researcher, supported by Ilo and Unachukwu (2020), indicate a rising trend of poor academic outcomes among students despite the state government's consistent prioritization of education as a driver of socio-economic growth. Several studies (Agnes et al., 2022; Iviemu, 2017) have sought to identify underlying causes of this decline, pointing to factors such as examination anxiety.

Examination anxiety also referred to as test anxiety is a psychological condition characterized by extreme stress, fear, and discomfort before or during exams. It may cause concentration difficulties, physiological symptoms, and reduced academic performance. Horsfall and Wordu (2023) define it as irrational fear that may lead to avoidance behaviors, while Patil and Aithala (2017) note its situational nature, which affects students regardless of subject matter. Examination anxiety can be both beneficial and detrimental depending on its intensity. Okobia and Oji (2021) classify it into two forms: affective (somatic) anxiety, which includes physical symptoms like increased heart rate and muscle tension, and cognitive anxiety, which involves negative thoughts and self-doubt that impair focus and memory. As Amalu (2017) and Garcia et al. (2024) highlight, both types can significantly disrupt academic performance by interfering with cognitive and physiological processes. For the purpose of this study, the researcher defines examination anxiety as any emotional or psychological condition that hinders or enhances an individual's ability to perform effectively in a testing situation. Furthermore, gender can play a significant role in shaping these experiences and conditions, as societal expectations and cultural norms often influence the development of examination anxiety differently in male students and female students.

Gender has been identified as a key factor in understanding examination anxiety and academic resilience. Gender encompasses the roles typically associated with being male or female. Society often uses gender to define the responsibilities assigned to male and female present. According to Kauffman as cited in Igbo et al. (2015), gender also relates to behaviours linked to masculinity and femininity, as well as individuals' perceptions of their roles as male or female. Consequently, gender shapes self-perception, with most individuals of the same sex associating with specific traits. These traits significantly impact children during their developmental years. Ray and Negi (2024) found that female students report higher anxiety during exams, which may be linked to societal pressures and the competitive nature of academic settings. Factors such as fear of failure, societal expectations, and academic demands significantly contribute to this heightened anxiety in female students (Chung & Chen, 2020). Conversely, male students often display lower anxiety levels, which could be attributed to different coping mechanisms and social behaviours (Chung & Chen, 2020). Examination anxiety can adversely affect academic performance, with female students facing more challenges in reaching their full potential due to higher anxiety levels (Ray & Negi, 2024).

Surprisingly, there is a lack of empirical evidence regarding the correlation between examination anxiety and academic performance of public secondary school students in Anambra State. The existing arguments regarding the relationship between the dimension of examination anxiety and academic performance have not been fully substantiated by empirical research in Anambra State. Therefore, the researcher addressed this gap by conducting a study that investigated the relationship between examination anxiety as correlate of academic performance among public secondary school students in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Ideally, students' academic performance in secondary schools in Anambra State should serve as a strong indicator of educational success which is reflected in high pass rates, consistent improvement in grades, fulfillment of minimum academic standards and successful progression to higher education or vocational opportunities. However, the researcher has observed with growing concern that the academic performance of students in many public secondary schools across the state falls significantly short of these expectations. Field observations reveal persistent issues such as low examination scores, high rates of class repetition, and widespread underperformance in key subjects. These trends suggest that a substantial number of students are struggling to meet basic academic requirements, despite the provision of instructional resources and qualified teachers. Moreover, students often appear unprepared for major examinations, pointing to deeper underlying issues beyond instructional quality or curriculum delivery. If this situation continues unchecked, it could undermine the state's efforts to build a strong and educated workforce, weaken its human capital development, and potentially lead to higher dropout rates. The long-term implications may include increased social problems such as unemployment, youth restiveness, and crime. Given these concerns, the present study investigates whether factors such as examination anxiety are significantly related to students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The study was to investigate the relationship between examination anxiety as correlate of academic performance of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of public secondary students in Anambra State.
2. Investigate the relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of male and female public secondary students in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of public secondary students in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of male and female public secondary students in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There would be no significant relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of public secondary students in Anambra State.
2. There would be no significant relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of male and female public secondary students in Anambra State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted correlational research design. The study population consisted of 21,272 senior secondary school two (SS2) students drawn from 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. This comprised 9,550 male and 11,722 female students. SS2 students were selected for the study because they were not involved in any external examinations, thus making them more available and focused for the research. They were also considered academically mature enough to comprehend and respond appropriately to the research instruments. The population distribution data was obtained from the Planning, Research and Statistics Department of the Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC), Awka, Anambra State. A sample of 400 students, equally divided between males and females, was selected using a multistage sampling procedure. At the first stage, simple random sampling was used to choose two education zones: Awka and Nnewi. From each of these zones, five public secondary schools were selected through stratified random sampling, making a total of ten schools. In the final stage, a cluster sampling technique was employed, selecting one SS2 class from each school. Each class contributed 40 students, resulting in a total of 400 participants.

Two standardized instruments were used for data collection: the Westside Test Anxiety Scale (WTAS) by Driscoll (2004) and the Academic Performance Scale (APS) by Birchmeier et al. (2015). The WTAS measured test anxiety using 10 items on a 5-point Likert scale. The ARS-30 assessed academic resilience with 30 items, also on a 5-point scale. The APS evaluated academic performance using 8 items on a similar scale. These instruments had been widely applied across different cultures and within Nigerian contexts by previous researchers such as Amalu (2017), Akinola and Oredein (2021), and Esuong and Udo (2022). Although already standardized, the instruments were reviewed and approved for face validity by the researcher’s supervisor and three experts from the Faculty of Education. No modifications were made to any of the items. The reliability of the instruments was confirmed through a pilot test conducted with 20 SS2 students from five schools in Enugu State, which shares similar characteristics with the study area.

The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients were 0.88 for the WTAS, and 0.90 for the APS, confirming that the instruments were reliable for the study. The researcher, assisted by five trained research assistants, personally administered the 400 questionnaires to the selected students over a two-week period. Instruments were distributed and retrieved on the spot within the classrooms, and follow-up visits were made for students unable to complete the questionnaires immediately. A total of 376 properly completed questionnaires were returned, yielding a 94% return rate, while 24 were either incomplete or lost, accounting for a 6% loss rate. The 376 valid responses were used for data analysis. Data were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions and test hypotheses one and two. The strength of relationships was interpreted using standard correlation coefficient ranges. In hypothesis testing, a p-value less than or equal to 0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, while a p-value greater than 0.05 we did not reject the null hypotheses. All statistical computations were carried out using SPSS version 26.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of public secondary students in Anambra State?*

Table 1. Pearson’s Correlation between Examination Anxiety and Academic Performance of Public Secondary School Students in Anambra State

Variables	N	r	Remark
Examination Anxiety Scores	376	-0.24	Low Negative Relationship
Academic Performance scores			

Data in Table 1 showed the result of the Pearson’s correlation between examination anxiety scores and academic performance scores of secondary school students in Anambra State. A Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) of -0.24 was obtained. This value indicated that there was a low negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among secondary school students in Anambra State. This implies that as examination anxiety increases, academic performance decreases but at a low rate.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of male and female public secondary students in Anambra State?*

Table 2. Pearson’s Correlation Between Examination Anxiety and Academic Performance of Public Secondary School Students in Anambra State

Variables	N	r	Remark
Male:			
Examination Anxiety Scores	161	0.17	Very low positive relationship
Academic Performance scores			
Female:			
Examination Anxiety Scores	215	-0.33	Low negative relationship
Academic Performance scores			

Table 2 presented disaggregated result of the Pearson’s correlation between examination anxiety scores and academic performance by gender. The correlation coefficient for the male student was 0.17 which indicated a very low positive relationship. On the other hand, there was a low negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among female students as shown by the $r = -0.33$. The results imply that there was a difference in the size and direction of the relationship between the two variables for the two genders. For the males, an increase in examination anxiety results in an increase in academic performance but at a very low degree whereas for the females, as examination increases, their academic performance decreases at low rate.

Hypothesis 1

There would be no significant relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of public secondary students in Anambra State.

Table 3. Test of Significance of Pearson’s Correlation Between Examination Anxiety and Academic Performance of Public Secondary School Students in Anambra State

Variables	N	r	p	Remark
Examination Anxiety Scores	376	-0.24	0.00	Significant
Academic Performance scores				

The result displayed in Table 3 showed there was a significant negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Anambra State, $r = -0.24$, $p = 0.00$. Since the p value was less than 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There would be no significant relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of male and female public secondary students in Anambra State.

Table 4. Test of Significance of Pearson's Correlation Between Examination Anxiety and Academic Performance of Public Secondary School Students in Anambra State

Variables	N	r	p	Remark
Male:				
Examination Anxiety Scores	161	0.17	0.03	Significant
Academic Performance scores				
Female:				
Examination Anxiety Scores	215	-0.33	0.00	Significant
Academic Performance scores				

As shown in Table 4, there was a significant positive relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among male secondary school students, $r = 0.17$, $p=0.03$. Furthermore, the negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of female secondary school students in Anambra State was statistically significant, $r = -0.33$, $p=0.00$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that there was a low negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among secondary school students in Anambra State. One possible reason for this finding is that some level of anxiety can act as a motivator, prompting students to prepare better for examinations, thereby mitigating its negative impact. Another reason could be that students in Anambra State may have developed coping strategies to manage their anxiety effectively, reducing its detrimental effects on their academic performance. This finding is in agreement with Okobia and Oji (2021) who found a negative relationship between test anxiety and academic performance among undergraduate students in Nigeria. Okobia and Oji stated that test anxiety had a slight but significant impact on students' cumulative grade point average (CGPA). Similarly, Alemu and Feyssa (2020) found a significant negative relationship between test anxiety and students' achievement scores in Ethiopia. This means that cognitive factors contribute more to examination anxiety than affective factors.

Furthermore, there was a significant negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of students in public secondary. This result corroborates with Ali et al. (2021) who reported a low but significant negative relationship of cognitive test anxiety on students' examination. Similarly, Orakwue and Okigbo (2023) found that cognitive test anxiety significantly predicted achievement in Biology, reinforcing the notion that anxiety can negatively influence academic outcomes.

The findings of the study indicated that there was a low positive relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among male students, while there was a low negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. These findings suggest that while examination anxiety may slightly motivate male students to perform better academically, it tends to hinder academic performance among female students. Several factors may account for these findings. First, male students may perceive examination anxiety as a challenge that propels them to engage in more effective study habits, thereby leading to better academic performance. On the other hand, female students may experience heightened levels of test anxiety, which could negatively affect their ability to recall information and perform optimally under

examination conditions. Also, societal expectations and gender roles may contribute to the observed differences, as female students may feel greater pressure to excel academically, leading to increased anxiety levels that adversely impact performance. The findings of the present study was in agreement with Ali et al. (2021) who found that female students reported higher levels of cognitive test anxiety than their male counterparts. Furthermore, Ali et al. (2021) observed a small but significant negative effect of cognitive test anxiety on students' examination performance, accounting for 10% of the variance in academic performance. This is consistent with the present study's finding that examination anxiety negatively affects female students' academic performance. Similarly, Alemu and Feyssa (2020) also found that female students reported significantly higher test anxiety levels than male students. This supports the present study's results, as it reinforces the notion that test anxiety disproportionately affects female students, leading to lower academic performance. Furthermore, the findings of Bethel-Eke and Ikpa (2017) support the current study's results. Bethel-Eke and Ikpa (2017) found that cognitive test anxiety significantly influences students' academic performance and that gender differences exist in students' reactions to test anxiety. Bethel-Eke and Ikpa observed that male and female students responded differently to failure anticipation and intrusive thoughts, which aligns with the findings of the present study which revealed that male students exhibit a low positive relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance, while female students demonstrate a low negative relationship. Furthermore, there was a significant positive relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance among male secondary school students. Conversely, there was a significant negative relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance of female secondary school students in Anambra State. The findings of this study indicated a contrasting relationship between examination anxiety and academic performance based on gender. The finding of the study is in consonance with Ali et al. (2021) who found that female students exhibited higher levels of cognitive test anxiety compared to their male counterparts, with a small but significant negative effect on their academic performance. In the same vein, Alemu and Feyssa (2020) reported a significant negative correlation between test anxiety and students' academic performance. This means that female students were more prone to experiencing higher test anxiety levels. Conversely, Bethel-Eke and Ikpa (2017) suggested that cognitive examination anxiety could have a positive effect on academic performance in some cases, particularly when anxiety levels remained within a manageable range, as observed among male students in this study. The study by Okobia and Oji (2021) also supports this gender-based variation, indicating that while examination anxiety generally hampers academic achievement, the impact may differ between male and female students.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that there is a low positive relationship among examination anxiety and academic performance of public secondary school students in Anambra State. Specifically, examination anxiety showed a low positive relationship with academic performance among male students and a low negative relationship among female students. It is therefore pertinent that measures are put in place to improve students' academic performance in secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher proffers the following recommendations:

1. Administrators of public secondary schools should in collaboration with the school guidance counsellor(s) introduce structured anxiety management programmes for students. These could include mindfulness training, relaxation exercises, and cognitive-behavioural interventions to help students develop coping mechanisms.
2. Administrators of secondary schools should develop gender-sensitive intervention programmes to help male and female students manage examination anxiety effectively. Female students should be provided with targeted psychological and emotional support, such as counselling and mindfulness training, to mitigate the negative effects of examination anxiety on their academic performance.

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